

EFFECT OF FABRICATION PROCESS ON THE ELECTRICAL AND MORPHOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF MWNT-EPOXY COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

In this work the electrical transition from insulator to conductive behaviour of a fixed Multiwalled Carbon Nanotubes (MWNT) concentration epoxy based nanocomposite was tuned through process parameters control. A correlation has been proposed between the electrical behaviour and the developed nanocomposite microstructure through optical the microscopy analysis and the Small- Angle X-ray Scattering (SAXS) characterization.

Keywords: Carbon Nanotubes, composites, dispersion, electrical properties, percolation

INTRODUCTION

In the field of composite materials a promising approach for the development of engineered materials is the use of nanoparticles as fillers in polymeric matrices. Because of Carbon Nanotubes (CNT) unique physical properties, such as mechanical, thermal and electrical, many attempts have been done in order to fabricate CNTs composite materials. Actually, the bottleneck for CNTs application in composite field consists in the difficulty of controlling their dispersion in polymer matrices. In fact, as a result of strong van der Waals interactions, as produced CNTs are tightly stitched in bundles of several tubes, rendering the carbon-powder insoluble in aqueous and organic liquids and thus unprocessable.

The desired physical properties have been mainly obtained by varying the concentration of CNTs in the matrix, providing a insulator to conductor transition and a big improvement of mechanical stiffness and strength. Experimental results show that high electrical conductivity and improved mechanical properties can be reached in a wide range of polymers, such as thermoplastic and thermoset matrices at relatively low CNTs contents and it was assessed that the effective utilization of CNTs in composites primarily depends on the ability to control the dispersion not only at single tube level but at level of developing network within the polymer matrix. As conductive fillers, CNTs are able to decrease the overall resistivity of the polymer by several orders of magnitude when a network develops within the matrix, corresponding to the percolation phenomenon [1-2].

Recently, it was demonstrated that the tailoring of composites physical properties is not only related to CNTs concentration, but primarily to the ability of tuning the formed network morphology to provide the optimization of the final nanocomposite properties

[3]. Experimental results showed the existence of a multiscale dispersion state, where nanotubes form hierarchical structured networks of micro aggregates constituted by CNTs networks themselves.

The aim of this study is to show how it is possible to tune the electrical transition from insulator to conductive behaviour of a fixed Multiwalled Carbon Nanotubes (MWNT) concentration epoxy based nanocomposite through the process parameters control. Optical microscopy and Small- Angle X-ray Scattering (SAXS) analysis have been compared with electrical conductivity results and a correlation between the electrical behaviour and the multi levels structure has been attempted.

The percolation threshold can be theoretically calculated depending on the geometry of the conductive filler and using different approach. For a statistical distribution of filler particles, using the excluded volume concept, the percolation volumetric threshold can be evaluated as $\Phi = \frac{1}{2} * D/L$, in the limit of a large aspect ratio, such as that related to CNTs. Hence, considering a typical $L/D = 1000$ for CNTs, statistical percolation threshold for nanotubes systems is about 0.1wt% [4].

However, statistic theories consider a static medium as matrix, in which particles are randomly dispersed and don't take into account the possibility of interparticle field potential. Recent experimental results show that a kinetic percolation can be induced in a nanocomposite by diffusional migration or other perturbing external forces, such as shear. In this case, the particles can diffuse within the matrix, organise under the interparticle sticking potential and consequently form conducting networks at lower concentrations than the statistical one. Re-aggregation and flocculation phenomena are responsible for the formation of highly conductive networks at concentration much lower than the statistical percolation, while are totally ineffective above this limit [5-7]. Particle flocculation process strictly depends on the dispersion technique because is driven by external forces, such as temperature, shear, viscosity changes and chemical affinity with the surrounding matrix.

Hence, the improvement of composites physical properties is related not only to the ability to provide a dispersion at single nanotube level in the matrix, but also to the possibility of tuning the formed network morphology providing the optimization of the desired properties.

However, contradicting results have been found out regarding the dependence of percolation threshold on the CNTs aspect ratio. These contradictions were born from the substantial differences between the kinetic and the statistical percolation. In the second case, in fact, percolation threshold decreases upon an increase of aspect ratio, as theoretical results report, while in the second case, percolation threshold increases upon an increase of nanotubes length, because the bigger mass of the tubes hinder the particles diffusion.

Up to now, experimental results have shown that the electrical conductivity of composites with identical CNTs concentration and same matrix vary by only one or two orders of magnitude. A wider range of conductivities, bigger than 10 orders of magnitude, can be found if different matrices are considered [4].

In this work we show that a drop of eight orders of magnitude of electrical conductivity was found for the same matrix nanocomposite at a fixed concentration by varying the sonication medium and the curing temperature of the epoxy system. Microscopic analysis describing the morphology of CNTs agglomeration is correlated to the electrical results. Moreover, Small Angle X-ray Scattering technique is used to obtain information about the submicron-scale structures forming the CNTs agglomerates.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials and techniques

Nanocomposites based on epoxy resin and Multiwalled Carbon Nanotubes (MWNT) have been produced.

MWNT 3150 produced by catalytic carbon vapour deposition (CCVD) process were supplied by Nanocyl S.A.. The tubes have an average diameter of 9.5 nm, an average length less than 1 μm and a purity exceeding 95% (with less than 5% of metal oxide impurity).

The matrix is a bisphenol-A/epichlorohydrin derived liquid epoxy resin (Epon 828) with an aliphatic amine-based curing agent, triethylenetetramine, TETA (Epikure 3234) both supplied by Hexion. MWNT have an aspect ratio less than 100, so the expected statistical percolation threshold is about 1 wt%. The fixed MWNTs concentration used to prepare the epoxy nanocomposites is 0.05 wt%, hence a value much lower than the statistical one.

The nanocomposites production went through the following steps:

1. dispersion of nanotubes in TETA or Epon using sonication technique;
2. addition of the second element, such as TETA or Epon in stoichiometric ratio (13 phr); manual mixing;
3. curing in isothermal conditions.

Sonication was used as dispersing technique, carried out by means of a dipping tip ultrasonicator (Misonix S4000) both in TETA and DGEBA.

From the final composite at a fixed MWNT wt%, three different nanocomposites have been produced curing at three temperatures: 25, 70 and 120 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, with a postcuring at 120 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 2 hours for the first two samples.

As shown in table 1, materials can be divided into three groups depending on the production technique: one is related to the pure epoxy produced simply by mixing DGEBA and TETA (P1 P2, P3); the second one refers to the nanocomposites produced by sonication in TETA (T1, T2 and T3) and the third one to the nanocomposites produced by means of sonication in DGEBA (E1, E2 and E3). Each set of samples was cured respectively at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, 70 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 120 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

In order to visualize the MWNT microstructure, transmission optical micrographs were taken on samples having a thickness greater than the average nanotube cluster size.

An electrical characterization was carried out on the prepared nanocomposites for the evaluation of the dependence of the electrical conductivity on the production technique. Samples with a thickness of about 1 mm were polished and 50 mm^2 circular electrodes were painted on the largest surfaces with silver conductive paint.

The DC electrical conductivity was calculated from the electrical current measured using a pico-ammeter connected to a two-probes station (Signatone 1160 probe station). The probes were pointed to the silver electrodes on the sample largest surfaces, so that the current circulating in the thickness was measured applying a constant voltage of 40 V.

SAXS experiments were performed with a SAXSess Instrument manufactured by Anton Paar, with copper K_{α} radiation $\lambda = 0.1542$ nm equipped with a 2D imaging plate detection system. The X-Ray generator was operated at 40 kV and 50 mA. It was used a line collimation to ensure a high radiation intensity. The measurements were performed

samples in the form of thin films. The q-range analyzed was $0.07 \div 1 \text{ nm}^{-1}$, where q is the magnitude of scattering vector:

$$q = \frac{4\pi}{\lambda} \sin \theta$$

and 2θ is the scattering angle. Each spectrum was collected for 90 minutes in order to assure a good signal/noise ratio.

The procedure used to process the spectra involved different steps: 1) subtraction of the dark current; 2) normalization of the primary beam; 3) normalization for the transmittance value, is calculated dividing the scattering intensity by the sample's thickness; 4) subtraction of the background consisting of neat epoxy; 5) subtraction of the incoherent scattering and 6) correction for de-smearing. The background spectra are related to the neat epoxy samples obtained accordingly to the several curing procedures previously described.

Table 1 – Nanocomposites production process

SAMPLE	MATERIAL	PROCESS	CURING CYCLE	PRODUCTION TECHNIQUE
P1	Pure epoxy	Mixing Epon and TETA	24h@ 25° + 2h@120°C	1
P2			1h@ 70°C + 2h@120°C	2
P3			2h@120°C	3
T1	Nanocomposite	Sonication of MWNT in TETA	24h@ 25°C + 2h@120°C	4
T2			1h@ 70°C + 2h@120°C	5
T3			2h@120°C	6
D1		Sonication of MWNT in DGEBA	24h@ 25° + 2h@120°C	7
D2			1h@ 70°C + 2h@120°C	8
D3			2h@120°C	9

Results and discussion

Electrical conductivity measurements

In fig. 1 the electrical conductivity is plotted against the production techniques, which vary for the sonication medium and curing temperature. Nanocomposites can be divided into two groups, one related to the sonication in TETA (T1, T2 and T3) and the other to the sonication in DGEBA (D1, D2 and D3). Each set of samples was cured respectively at 25 °C, 70 °C and 120 °C. As a reference the conductivities of the three pure epoxy samples are reported (P1 P2, P3).

Figure 1 - Electrical conductivity of the epoxy based materials described in table 1 as a function of the production technique

The impressive result is that the conductivity increases from 5×10^{-11} S/m for the sample T1 to 4×10^{-7} S/m for the sample T3, respectively cured at 25 °C and 120 °C. For the second set of samples, the conductivity doesn't show a comparable increase passing from 25 °C to 120 °C cured samples, but the initial value related to room temperature cured composite is high, such as samples D1, D2 and D3 behave like conductors.

A so strong variation of electrical conductivity with curing temperature must be necessary related to differences in the microstructure present in the nanocomposites.

Microscopic analysis

For our purposes, microscopic analysis assesses the correlation between microstructure and electrical properties, showing a strict dependence of the composites microstructure on the curing temperature for the nanocomposites produced sonicating MWNTs in TETA. In fig. 2 differences in the aggregates microstructure for T1, T2 and T3 samples are evident. Aggregates dimension increases upon an increase of the curing temperature. This microstructure evolution can be explained by diffusional migration of the MWNTs induced by the higher temperature, due to changes in viscosity of the system and to the increase of kinetic energy of the particles. The viscosity of the matrix at 70 and 120 °C is lower than that of room temperature, hence the agglomeration process is accelerated. Contemporary, the gel time is as shorter as the temperature increases, leading to a fast increase of viscosity that freezes the microstructure after the aggregation, providing the formation of CNTs networks. This can lead to the observation that in our case, aggregation phenomena rapidly occur in the nanocomposites, having a kinetics that is faster than the gelation one. In our case, an increase of aggregates dimension corresponds to an increase of electrical conductivity.

Figure 2 - Transmission light micrographs of 0.05 MWNT wt% 30' sonicated in TETA samples processed at different curing temperatures (4, 5 and 6) as mentioned in table 1

A higher and more levelled conductivity characterizes D samples, where no evident changes in microstructure are observable by microscopic analysis (fig. 3a). In these samples, a higher magnification (20X) reveals a uniform and homogeneous dispersion, even at a submicron level (fig. 3b). The texture uniformity at different observation scale is responsible for the conductivity independence on the curing temperature.

The good affinity between nanotubes and epoxy resin provides composite solutions stable in time with a very fine dispersion, that is retained in the final cured composites.

Figure 3 - Transmission light micrographs of 0.05 MWNT wt% 30' sonicated in DGEBA samples processed at different curing temperatures (7,8 and 9) as mentioned in table 1 at a) 5X and b) 20X magnification

Small Angle X-ray Scattering analysis

The diffraction techniques are ideal tools for investigating the structure of CNTs dispersed in suspension or in polymeric materials. By using diffraction techniques based on light, neutron or X-ray beam, several research groups have evidenced that CNTs show a hierarchical structure consisting of micro-sized aggregates, which are constituted by bundles of a few hundreds nanometers diameter, at a nano-scale

dimensions. It is worth noting that in the length scale investigated by Small angle X-Ray Scattering (SAXS) analysis (i.e. a characteristic dimension not higher than one hundred nanometers) generally the scattered intensity follows a power law, interpreted as due to the presence of branched rope-like structures constituting the agglomerates. In other words, the dimensions of both the agglomerates and the bundles cannot be detected by diffraction features in the SAXS analysis. Furthermore, even if all diffraction features are badly affected by the low scattering contrast between CNTs and matrix, the general information of the fractal structures in disordered bundles are preserved [9-11].

In this study, SAXS technique is used to assess the nanoscale morphology of MWNTs in the produced epoxy nanocomposites. The morphology of CNTs, characterized by highly branched aggregates constituted by bundles with different dimensions randomly oriented in the space, can be described as being fractal objects. A fractal object can be defined as a self-similar object over a large range of sizes, or in the other words, an object whose structure appears similar at different magnifications within each scale range. In order to assess the fractal dimension, the Porod plot i.e. $\log I$ vs $\log q$ is used. It gives an indication of the fractal nature of nanotubes' structure, as the slope of the linear region, P . The mass fractal dimension, $D_m = -P$, is a measure of the compactness of the mass fractal object and describes volume distribution of a mass m , as $m \sim r^{D_m}$, where r is the radius of the fractal object. The relation $1 < D_m < 3$ holds for the mass fractal. The smaller is the mass fractal dimension the more "open" is structure investigated; on the other hand, an increase in the fractal dimension implies more compact structure of scattering domains. Furthermore when $-4 < P < -3$ the observed objects have fractal surface with fractal dimension D_s ranging from 2 to 3 ($P = D_s - 6$); a fractal surface dimension 2 corresponds for the Porod law to a smooth surface boundary.

In figure 4 are reported the diffraction spectra related to the neat epoxy sample and the nanocomposites obtained by dispersing nanotubes in TETA and DGEBA all cured at 70°C (P2, T2 and D2). The scattering data are cut at 5 nm^{-1} . All spectra exhibit both a diffraction halo at 3.5 nm^{-1} , which is attributed to the pseudo-ordered epoxy structure and an increase of the scattering intensity at lower q values due to the epoxy structure and the presence of nanotubes. It is worth noting that the halo at $q=3.5 \text{ nm}^{-1}$ is not affected by the nanotubes and so this peak can be assumed as an internal reference. In this way it has been possible to perform accurately the subtraction of the matrix in order to isolate the nanotubes diffraction features from the nanocomposites spectra.

Figure 5 reports the Porod plot of T3 and D3 samples. The results indicate the presence of a fractal geometry (mass or surface fractal) in the length scale between 6 and 80 nm (where the length scale values, l were calculated assuming that $l=2\pi/q$, where q are respectively the maximum and minimum values at which the scattered intensity can be well detected without any errors) [12].

The power law scattering in the region $0.07 < q < 1 \text{ nm}^{-1}$ with a slope \square in the range between 2 and 3, is characteristic of branched or disordered structures consisting of thin bundles inside the nano-ropes [9] The power law slope in the range between 3 and 4 should be due to the presence of ropes with fractal surface (i.e. single nanotubes not aligned in the direction of the rope). It is worth noting that the absence of a q -region with slopes close to 1 is an indicative evidence of nanotubes aggregation.

Figure 4 - SAXS spectra of neat epoxy sample and T and D nanocomposites cured at 70 °C

Figure 5 - Background subtracted SAXS spectra for T3 and D3 nanocomposites cured at 120°C

Regardless the experimental procedures adopted for the curing, all samples investigated show linear scattering behaviour all over the length scale investigated. The results in

terms of D_m (or D_s), characteristic size and the linear q -range interval considered are reported in Table 2.

Table 2 - Characteristic parameters of the power law behaviour of T and D nanocomposites

Samples	Size [nm]	D_m and D_s	q range [nm^{-1}]
D1	50	$D_m = 2.52$	$0.126 \div 0.47$
T1	>78	$D_m = 2.5$	$0.08 \div 0.4$
D2	-		-
T2	>96	$D_m = 2.55$	$0.065 \div 0.27$
D3	>90	$D_s = 2.68$	$0.07 \div 0.44$
T3	>86	$D_m = 2.72$	$0.073 \div 0.45$

Since isolated ropes, bundles and a large fraction of aggregates coexist in the nanocomposites, and all contribute to the scattered intensity, it is hard to rationalize the power law-slopes based on any simple model. However, it is possible inferring that for a sonication time equal to 30 minutes, the micro sized aggregates or bundles are sufficiently opened and break-up to produce ropes with internal fractal structure. The SAXS analysis does not allow to discriminate any difference in the morphology at nano-scale level for both T and D sets of nanocomposites.

CONCLUSIONS

In summary, Multiwalled Carbon Nanotubes/Epoxy composites has been produced whose fixed composition is below the statistical percolation threshold. Manufacturing operative parameters such as the medium (resin or hardener) within the sonication mixing has been performed and the curing temperatures has permitted the smooth modulation over eight orders of magnitude of the insulator to conductor electrical transition. Such result has been possible by tuning the aggregation status of the carbon nanotubes within the matrix. Sonication medium plays a major role in determining the final electrical properties of the composites and, when, the carbon nanotubes have been dispersed into the ammine hardener the curing temperature can tune the reaggregation process to produce a full modulation of electrical conductivity.

Micro and nano scale structure of the manufactured composites has been investigated by optical transmission technique and SAXS analysis, respectively. SAXS experiments lead to the conclusion that the nanocomposites nano-scale structure is almost the same both for T and D sets of nanocomposites, while optical transmission microscopy has revealed an increase in size of the nanotubes aggregates as the cure temperature. Hence the differences in the electrical conductivity have to be ascribed to the micro-length scale morphological differences. Further analysis is in progress to assess quantitatively such experimental findings.

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